

Survey on the GitHub Copilot Adoption

FREE AND CLARIFIED CONSENT TERM (FCCT)

You are being invited to participate in the research entitled "**Enablers and Impediments of Adopting GitHub Copilot in Large Companies: An Empirical Study**". This study examines how users adopt and utilize a code completion technology called GitHub Copilot.

Participation: The experiment is divided into two parts. First, you will be asked a series of objective questions about yourself. Then, in the second part, you will be asked about the factors that motivate or would motivate the adoption and use of GitHub Copilot as an assistant for day-to-day activities. We estimate that the experiment will take between 5 and 7 minutes.

Confidentiality and anonymity: The information in this research is strictly confidential, disclosed only in scientific events or publications and will only be used for this purpose, with no identification of the participant(s) ensuring full confidentiality about their participation.

Contact information for those responsible for the research: During the research period, you have the right to ask any questions or ask for any other clarification, simply contacting the principal researcher by the emails iury.oliveira@ensino.ipt.br / iuryoliveira@hotmail.com.

Voluntary Participation: You have the right to refuse to participate in the referred survey or to withdraw from this study, at any time, without prejudice or retaliation, for your voluntary decision. To quit, leave the site before completing the survey.

Data retention: The data will be kept after the completion of the project for 5 years.

* Indicates required question

Participant Data

For this first session, we ask you to tell us a little about yourself, your professional experience and experience with GitHub Copilot. The objective is to analyze the profile of the people who are contributing to the work.

1. How old are you? *

Mark only one oval.

- Between 18 and 25 years old
- Between 26 and 35 years old
- Between 36 and 45 years old
- Over 46 years old

2. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- I prefer not to inform
- I prefer to describe myself

3. How long have you been working with software development? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than de 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- 10 years or more

4. What is your main area of expertise in the software development process? *

Mark only one oval.

- Software development
- Software project management
- Systems analyst
- Software testing
- Software architecture
- Information security
- Infrastructure and networks
- Database

5. What type of company do you currently work for? *

Mark only one oval.

- Micro company (up to 10 employees)
- Small company (from 11 to 50 employees)
- Medium company (from 51 to 250 employees)
- Large company (more than 250 employees)

6. What is your role in the company? *

Mark only one oval.

- Junior developer
- Mid-level developer
- Senior Developer
- Technical lead
- Architect
- Systems Analyst
- Test Analyst / tester
- Infrastructure and networks analyst
- SRE
- Security Analyst

7. What programming languages do you currently work in? *

Check all that apply.

- Java
- Python
- JavaScript
- Ruby
- PHP
- TypeScript
- C#
- C/C++
- Go
- Other: _____

8. How long have you known about Artificial Intelligence-based code writing assistants like GH Copilot, Code Whisperer, AlphaCode or others? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- I had never heard about this topic.

9. Is there a plan for adoption/use of Copilot by your current company? *

Mark only one oval.

- We already use it in my company.
- The company plans to adopt in the next 12 months.
- There is no plan / initiative to adopt /use.

10. How often do you use GitHub Copilot in your software projects? *

Mark only one oval.

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Never

GitHub Copilot Adoption Technical Session

For this session we ask you to answer what your experience has been using GitHub Copilot or what you imagine your experience in an adoption case could be like.

11. Performance Expectancy (PE) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Copilot reduces the time spent creating new codes.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot decreases the time spent understanding and reviewing code.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot reduces the time spent refactoring and modifying code.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot decreases the time spent creating unit tests.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot reduces the time spent documenting code.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot reduces my time searching for solutions.	<input type="radio"/>				

Copilot reduces effort in repetitive activities.

<input type="radio"/>				
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Copilot makes my team work better together.

<input type="radio"/>				
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12. Effort Expectancy (EE) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Copilot makes it easy to create new codes.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot makes code understanding and reviewing easier.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot makes it easy to refactor and modify code.	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Social Influence (SI) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
People see me as a more modern professional if I use Copilot.	<input type="radio"/>				
Leaders in my organization encourage the use of Copilot.	<input type="radio"/>				
Did watching other professionals use GitHub Copilot successfully influence your decision to adopt it?	<input type="radio"/>				
I would be more inclined to use GitHub Copilot if experts or people in the programming community recommended it	<input type="radio"/>				
Do you feel pressured to adopt GitHub Copilot because it has become a	<input type="radio"/>				

Widely
accepted tool
in the
developer
community?

14. Facilitating condition *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The fact that it was available in my IDE made adoption easier.	<input type="radio"/>				
The existing documentation and examples facilitated the adoption of Copilot.	<input type="radio"/>				
It made adoption easier due to the plan created by my organization.	<input type="radio"/>				

15. Hedonic Motivation (HM) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Copilot is pleasant to work with.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot is fun to work with.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel more fulfilled with my work working with Copilot	<input type="radio"/>				

16. Learning Value (LV) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Copilot helps me learn new programming techniques.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot helps me solidify my learning of certain topics.	<input type="radio"/>				
Copilot helps me learn new ways to solve programming problems.	<input type="radio"/>				

17. Habit (HT) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
After using Copilot, it would be difficult to work without	<input type="radio"/>				
Using Copilot helps me create good coding habits.	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Are there any additional comments you would like to share? *

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